

The Knowledge, Attitude and Some Factors Related to First Aid of Teachers at Some Primary Schools

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To describe the knowledge, attitudes and factors related to primary school teachers in Nam Dinh city.

Subject and method: Using a cross-sectional descriptive research design with a questionnaire survey on 394 primary school teachers in 10 primary schools in Nam Dinh city, Vietnam.

Results: The percentage of teachers who answered correctly about first aid for nosebleeds, sprains, and choking on food was high at 91.9%, 97.0%, 94.2% respectively, the percentage of correct answers about first aid was low at 3.3% burns, 7.1% drowning, 4.6% fractures. Especially, there was only 33% teachers with the satisfactory general knowledge about first aid. 62% teachers with the satisfactory attitude about initial first aid, 37.8% teachers with the unsatisfactory attitude. There was a correlation between the teachers' knowledge about first aid and years of work, having learned about first aid. Moreover, the teachers' attitude was related to the age group and previous experience of first aid.

Conclusion: The study showed that teachers' knowledge and attitude about first aid were not high. Thus, the training and communication programs were needed to improve knowledge about first aid for primary school teachers.

KEYWORDS: first aid, knowledge, attitude, primary school teachers

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INTRODUCTION

First aid can be defined as the immediate caring given to a person who has been injured or suddenly ill with materials available on hand to preserve life, alleviate suffering, prevent further illness or injury and promote recovery¹. The aim of first aid is to prevent or minimize potential harm as soon as possible before going to hospital. Therefore, timely first aid is essential if an accident occurs. Children are more susceptible to injury and higher risk due to developmental and behavioral characteristics such as unawareness of hazards, as well as physical characteristics like as smaller body mass and thinner, more vulnerable skin. In the event of an accident occurring at school, first aid before the victim is taken to the hospital is very important and teachers often act as the first responders². School teachers who provide first aid quickly can reduce the rate of students injury and death due to injury-related problems, so teachers need to have adequate knowledge and practice of basic first aid skills³.

First aid knowledge includes the understanding and skills needed to effectively respond and handle health emergencies, while also contributing to the prevention of possible risks¹. In addition to assessing first aid knowledge, analyzing attitude about first aid is very important⁴. Therefore, we conducted this study to investigate the knowledge, attitude and related factors of primary school teachers about first aid. Thus, measures can be taken to improve teachers' knowledge about first aid.

METHODS

Research setting

A cross-sectional descriptive study conducted on 394 primary school teachers in 10 primary schools in Nam Dinh city, Vietnam from March 2021 to October 2021.

Sample:

The sample size was calculated using the following formula

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$$n = Z_{(1-\alpha/2)}^2 \frac{p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

With $Z_{(1-\alpha/2)}$: 1.96 (95% confidence level); $d=0.05$ (5% error); $p=0.5$ (to maximize sample size).

Sampling technique: The convenient sample of teachers at primary schools in Nam Dinh city, Vietnam until the sample size was sufficient according to the calculated formula. In practice, the sample size was 394 teachers which ensure minimum sample size according to the formula calculated.

Measurements:

The questionnaire is based on the research of Nguyen Thi Khanh Linh⁵, including 16 questions about the teachers' knowledge and 9 questions about attitude of first aid. The questionnaire was revised and reviewed by experts. After that, it was conducted a pilot study. The knowledge is satisfactory if the total of correct answers is more than 50% of the total number of questions. The attitude is assessed on the Likert scale includes: In which strongly agree corresponds is 5 points, agree corresponds is 4 points, neutral corresponds is 3 points, disagree corresponds is 2 points, strongly disagree corresponds is 1 point. Total score ≥ 36 points indicates the satisfactory attitude, on the contrary, total score < 36 points indicates the unsatisfactory attitude.

Data collection

The researcher clearly explained the purpose of study and instructed how to fill out the survey form. Each research subject will be given a pre-printed questionnaire by the

researcher and completed at the primary school where the research was conducted. The researcher will collect the form after the research subject completes the survey form.

Research ethics: This study was conducted after approval by the Biomedical Ethics Council of Nam Dinh University of Nursing (No. 347/GCN-HDDD, February 26, 2021) and permission to conduct research from the Nam Dinh City Department of Education.

Statistical analysis: All variables entered into the regression models were coded or transformed into categorical measurements. Collected data were coded and tabulated using a personal computer. Using an SPSS 20.0 program for Windows. The chi square test was used to identify the associations of some factors to the teachers' knowledge and attitude about first aid which were coded as categorical variables.

RESULTS

General information of the research subjects

The study was conducted on 394 primary school teachers, the proportion of female teachers accounts for the majority of 91.9% and 8.1% male teachers; The age from 30 to 50 accounts for the majority with 64.3%; Most teachers have college and university degrees were 94.9%; Teachers with more than 10 years of working experience were 60.9%; The proportion who have heard about first aid and know about the importance of first aid was very high, 92.6% and 96.4% respectively; However, the number of teachers who have never done first aid and have not studied about first aid was high, 44.2% and 60.2% respectively.

Table 1. Research subjects responding to situations (N=394)

Contents	Incorrect answer		Correct answer	
	N	%	N	%
Emergency center phone number	15	3.8	379	96.2
Definition	38	9.6	356	90.4
Purpose	312	79.7	82	20.3
Principle	372	94.4	20	4.6
Arrange the steps of cardiopulmonary resuscitation	383	97.2	11	2.8
Treatment of venomous snake bites	312	67.5	132	33.5
First aid for arterial bleeding	263	66.8	131	33.2
First aid for fractures	376	95.4	18	4.6
First aid for drowning	366	92.9	28	7.1
First aid for electric shock	264	67.0	130	32.7
First aid for burns	381	96.7	13	3.3
First aid for fainting	87	22.1	307	77.9
First aid for choking on food	23	5.8	371	94.2
First aid for convulsion	264	67.0	130	32.7
First aid for sprains	12	3.0	382	97.0
First aid for nosebleeds	32	8.1	362	91.9

The percentage of teachers who answered correctly on the topics of emergency phone numbers was high at 92%,

definition of first aid 90.4%, first aid for sprains 97%, nosebleeds 91%, and first aid for fainting 77.9%. While the

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knowledge of principles was 4.6% and steps of first aid was 2.8%, and correct first aid for burns 3.3% were very low. The percentage of correct answers on the purpose of first aid was

only 20%, first aid for arterial bleeding was 33.2%, first aid for electric shock was 32.7%, and treatment of venomous snake bites was 33.2%.

Figure 1. General knowledge about first aid of teachers (N = 394)

Teachers with the unsatisfactory knowledge of first aid accounted for high percentage (67%).

Table 2. The attitude towards first aid of the research subject (N = 394)

Content	Attitude	Number	%
Frequency of searching for information about first aid	Satisfactory attitude	89	22.6
	Unsatisfactory attitude	305	77.4
The importance of first aid	Satisfactory attitude	305	77.7
	Unsatisfactory attitude	88	33.3
The importance of injury prevention	Satisfactory attitude	270	68.5
	Unsatisfactory attitude	124	31.5
The importance of knowing the first aid skills	Satisfactory attitude	365	92.6
	Unsatisfactory attitude	29	7.4
Anxiety if you don't know the first aid skills	Satisfactory attitude	132	33.5
	Unsatisfactory attitude	262	66.5
Training about first aid for everyone in the community	Satisfactory attitude	234	59.4
	Unsatisfactory attitude	160	40.6
The need to conduct first aid for victims	Satisfactory attitude	297	75.4
	Unsatisfactory attitude	97	24.6
The danger of no performing first aid for victims	Satisfactory attitude	372	91.4
	Unsatisfactory attitude	22	5.6
Attitude of teachers if they meet victims	Satisfactory attitude	212	53.8
	Unsatisfactory attitude	182	46.2

The majority of teachers have a satisfactory attitude about the importance of first aid. The percentage of teachers with a satisfactory attitude if they meet victims and the

frequency of searching for information about first aid was 53.8% and 22.6%, respectively.

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Figure 2: The mothers' attitude about first aid (N = 394)

The percentage of teachers with the satisfactory attitude about first aid was 62.2%. However, there was 37.8% teachers with the unsatisfactory attitude.

Table 3. Some factors related to the knowledge about first aid (N = 394)

Variables		Knowledge		OR (CI 95%)	P
		Unsatisfactory	Satisfactory		
The age group	≤30 years	79 (70.5%)	33 (29.5%)	1.25 (0.78-2.01)	0.21
	> 30 years	185 (65.6%)	97 (34.4%)		
Gender	Female	240 (66.3%)	112 (33.7%)	0.6 (0.28- 1.50)	0.21
	Male	24 (75%)	8 (25.0%)		
The educational level	Under university	106 (68.8%)	48 (31.2%)	1.14 (0.74- 1.76)	0.31
	University or higher	158(65.8%)	82 (34.2%)		
Number of working years	≤ 5 years	60 (81.1%)	14 (18.9%)	2.43 (1.30-4.55)	0.002
	> 5 years	204 (63.7%)	116 (36.3%)		
Having studied about first aid	No	150 (63.3%)	87 (36.7%)	4.57 (1.41- 2.10)	0.03
	Yes	43 (27.4%)	114 (72.6%)		
Having performed about first aid	No	112 (64.4%)	62 (35.6%)	0.80 (0.53- 1.23)	0.19
	Yes	152 (69.1%)	68 (30.9%)		
The need of training about first aid	No	6 (66.7%)	3 (33.3%)	0.98 (0.24- 4.00)	0.62
	Yes	255 (66.2%)	130 (33.8%)		

There was a relationship between teachers' knowledge and factors such as number of working years and having studied about first aid ($p < 0.05$)

Table 4. Some factors related to the attitude about first aid (N=394).

Variables		Attitude		OR (CI 95%)	P
		Unsatisfactory	Satisfactory		
The age group	≤30 years	54 (48.2%)	58 (51.8%)	1.83 (1.17- 2.86)	0.005
	> 30 years	95 (33.7%)	187 (66.3%)		
Gender	Female	137 (37.8%)	225 (62.2%)	1.01 (0.48- 2.14)	0.57
	Male	12 (60%)	8 (40%)		
The educational level	Under university	65 (42.2%)	89 (57.8%)	1.35 (0.89- 2.05)	0.09
	University or higher	84 (35.0%)	156 (65.0%)		
Number of working years	≤ 5 years	31 (41.9%)	43 (58.1%)	1.23 (0.73 -2.06)	0.25
	> 5 years	118 (36.9%)	202 (63.1%)		

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Having studied about first aid	No	92 (38.8%)	145 (61.2%)	1.11 (0.73- 1.68)	0.35
	Yes	57 (36.3%)	100 (63.7%)		
Having performed about first aid	No	114 (43.7%)	147 (56.3%)	1.56 (1.03- 2.35)	0.02
	Yes	44 (33.1%)	89 (66.9%)		
The need of training about first aid	No	5 (55.6%)	4 (44.4%)	2.20 (0.53-7.91)	0.22
	Yes	144 (37.4%)	254 (62.6%)		

There was a relationship between teachers' attitude and factors such as the age group and having performed about first aid ($p < 0.05$)

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of primary school teachers about first aid.

The percentage of teachers with knowledge of first aid was 33%, lower than other studies. The study of Wubet Taklual's in Ethiopia showed that 45.8% teachers were knowledgeable about first aid⁶. The study in Madinah, Saudi Arabia investigated "The prevalence of first aid knowledge among school instructors", the results showed that 44.8% had good knowledge of first aid⁷. The study indicated that primary school teachers' knowledge of first aid was still low. Teachers with the unsatisfactory knowledge of first aid accounted for high percentage (67%). The main reasons may be due to lack of proper training, ineffective communication methods or being influenced by false information from unofficial sources. Our study showed that teachers' knowledge gaps were highest in the topics of cardiopulmonary resuscitation, convulsions and snake bites. Up to 94% teachers lack of knowledge about cardiopulmonary resuscitation. This may be because these first aid cases are less common in practice, and teachers are not trained in first aid, only 39.8% teachers attended training courses or trained in first aid. The majority of teachers have good knowledge about the definition and principles of first aid, first aid for nosebleeds, first aid for fainting, first aid for convulsions, sprains and bleeding. All teachers have good knowledge about these first aid whether they have been trained or not. These may be common daily incidents that teachers or their friends and relatives often encounter.

The attitude about first aid of primary school teachers

Regarding attitude about first aid, only 53.8% teachers have a satisfactory attitude and they are ready to provide first aid to victims when they meet an accident occurs. While, 46.2% teachers still have a less interested attitude. Because our teachers are primary responsibility for the danger of their students. Some teachers do not care about first aid when an accident occurs, perhaps because it is responsibility of medical staff in the school. Due to inadequate awareness of first aid, teachers' attitude was low and they are worry when they do not know the first aid skills. In which, up to 77.4% teachers rarely and never seek information. Only 33.5% teachers are worried when they do not know the basic first aid skills. May be due to many difficulties in the process of studying about first aid. The study showed that the percentage of teachers with the satisfactory attitude about the importance of first aid was 77.7%. In addition, 92.6% teachers with the satisfactory attitude about the importance of knowing the first

aid skills. Thus, it can be seen that most of teachers recognized the importance of first aid. The results of the study showed that the percentage of teachers with the unsatisfactory attitude about first aid was high at 37.8%. The results showed that teachers were not fully aware of the role and importance of first aid in the school environment, so it was necessary to further strengthen educational activities, raise awareness and change teachers' attitudes towards first aid, in order to ensure maximum safety for students.

Factors affecting primary school teachers' first aid knowledge

The study found that experience and training in first aid were significantly related to teachers' first aid knowledge. The proportion of teachers with inadequate first aid knowledge in the group with less than five years of work experience was 81.1%, which was higher than that of the group with more than five years of experience (63.7%). Gemechu Ganfure's study also found that those with five to ten years of work experience were three times more likely to have knowledge than those with less than five years of work experience⁸. Workneh's study of kindergarten and primary school teachers in Gondar City, Northwestern Ethiopia also found that work experience was related to first aid knowledge³. Teachers with longer working experience often encounter more emergency situations during their work, which helps them improve their ability to recognize and handle situations related to first aid. In addition, they have more opportunities to attend training courses, seminars, or receive continuing education in first aid. This helps them improve their knowledge. This also explains the relationship between knowledge and first aid training. Most of the teachers who had attended first aid training courses had better first aid knowledge than the teachers who had not attended training. The results of the study showed that the percentage of teachers who had received first aid training and had satisfactory knowledge was 72.6%, which was significantly higher than that of the untrained group, with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.034$). This confirms the important role of first aid training in improving teachers' awareness and skills. This confirms the important role of first aid training in improving teachers' awareness and skills. This result was similar to the study by Gemechu Ganfure (2018) in Ethiopia⁸, which also noted that teachers who had attended first aid training had good knowledge, compared to the group who had not attended. These studies illustrated that first aid

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training not only improves teachers' cognitive skills but also increases their confidence in handling emergency situations.

Factors affecting primary school teachers' first aid attitude

The results of the study showed that the factors affecting teachers' initial first aid attitudes were age and having participated in first aid. Other studies have shown that work experience and previous first aid training was related to teachers' attitudes^{8, 9, 10}. The proportion of teachers over 30 years old with a positive attitude towards first aid (66.3%) was higher than that of teachers under 30 years old (51.8%). This result reflects a clear difference in attitude about first aid between the two age groups. Teachers over 30 years old may have accumulated more experience in teaching and may have faced more situations requiring first aid, which helps them form a more satisfactory attitude about first aid practices. This difference can also be explained by increased awareness and maturity in education, helping them realize the importance of equipping first aid skills. The study also showed that teachers who had received first aid training showed more satisfactory attitude and were more likely to respond quickly in emergency situations. Among the group of teachers who had participated in first aid, the percentage of teachers with the satisfactory attitude (66.9%) was more than teachers with the unsatisfactory attitude (33.1%). This shows that participating in first aid training courses plays an important role in improving teachers' satisfactory attitudes towards first aid skills.

CONCLUSION

The satisfactory knowledge and attitude about first aid among primary school teachers are limited. Therefore, the training courses and training programs should be organized to improve teachers' knowledge and skills. At the same time, communication sessions should be conducted to increase awareness about the importance of first aid skills in schools.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We confirm that there was no conflict of interest in this study.

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